

Information as a Conserved Quantity?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Sept. 6, 2025

A traditional approach to obtaining a probability distribution is to maximize an entropy function subject to constraints. One may note, however, that in the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) cases, one may obtain the same distribution through reaction balance, with no maximization required. One may also note that if the constraints are linked to conserved quantities as in $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = e_{ave}$ ((1)), then differentials of these are zero. As a result, a sum of the differential (derivative with respect to $p(e_i)$) of the entropy function must also sum to zero and so we suggest that entropy represents a conserved quantity just like the two constraints. In fact in the MB case, entropy - $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ is minus one multiplied by the average of information $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$. If information is a conserved quantity, one may write it as an average just as one writes $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = e_{ave}$ for conserved energy. In the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, one has two probabilities, $p(e_i)$ and $(1-p(e_i))$ and so creates a sum of average information which is conserved. Given that information is linked to $p(e_i)$ which is linked to e_i , the conservation of information is linked to the constraints ((1)), we argue. The information that is conserved, however, is a minimal amount of information so the notion of conserved information is completely compatible with maximized entropy subject to constraints, we argue.

Maximization of Entropy Subject to Constraints

A traditional approach to obtaining a probability distribution is to maximize entropy subject to constraints. Typical constraints (of conserved quantities) are:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \text{ and } \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = e_{ave} = E/N \quad ((1))$$

The entropy is taken to be the \ln of the number of states in the MB case

$$\ln(N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!) \text{ where } n(e_i) = N p(e_i) \quad ((2))$$

Stirling's approximation, $\ln(n(e_i)!) = n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i))$ ((3)) is then applied. Writing this in terms of $p(e_i)$, one has average information:

$$- \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((4))$$

The \ln of the number of states becomes average information under the Stirling approximation and one could just as well take this as a starting point, we argue. We now wish to examine the maximization process for the MB case.

$$d/dp(e_i) (- \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))) dp(e_i) = -e_i/T dp(e_i) + dp(e_i) \quad ((5))$$

$$((5)) \text{ yields } p(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((6))$$

The point we wish to make is that if one sums over i , then the RHS of ((5)) is zero, thus the LHS must also be zero. Thus, the LHS is like a constraint for a conserved quantity, namely information (from information science). In other words, there are three conserved quantities in this problem: information, energy and particle number. Given that information is linked to $p(e_i)$ and e_i , changes to information are linked to changes to the energy and particle number constraint. We suggest that the whole maximization of entropy with respect to constraints may be thought of in this way.

We also note that one may obtain the MB distribution directly from reaction balance:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_i + e_j \text{ and } p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_i)p(e_j) \text{ ((7))}$$

Taking \ln of the second equation and equating to $-1/T$ multiplied by the first yields the result. One does not need to use maximization of entropy/conservation of information at all to find the MB distribution. We suggest, however, that ((7)) is linked to information because it shows the probabilities which occur in interactions. In the MB case, it is simply $p(e_i)$ and so this is used to create the conserved information

$$\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \text{ ((8)) (entropy is } -1 \text{ multiplied by this quantity)}$$

In the FD and BE cases, the interaction is more complicated. Using reaction balance yields:

$$p(e_1) (1 - p(e_3)) p(e_2) (1 - p(e_4)) = p(e_3) (1 - p(e_1)) p(e_4) (1 - p(e_2)) \text{ ((9))}$$

One may see that two probabilities are at work, $p(e_i)$ and $(1 - p(e_i))$, although the latter is not normalized. We stress the importance of the physical probabilities present in an interaction (which create equilibrium). Mathematically, one may write: $p(e_i) / (1 - p(e_i))$ which appears to be one enhanced/reduced probability, but physically there are two probabilities linked with two physical processes. The first is the probability to have an e_i present ($p(e_i)$) to react and the second $(1 - p(e_i))$ is a reduction/enhancement probability involved in the reaction. Thus, the probability to have an e_i ($p(e_i)$) is not enough to ensure a reaction in the FD case (and does not capture the full probability of reaction in the BE case. The conserved information is now:

$$\text{FD } p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) + (1 - p(e_i)) \ln(1 - p(e_i)) \text{ ((10a))}$$

$$\text{BE } p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) - (1 + p(e_i)) \ln(1 + p(e_i)) \text{ ((10b))}$$

It is a combination of the two information $\ln(p(e_i))$ and $\ln(1 - p(e_i))$ which yields $-e_i/T$, i.e.

$$dp(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)/(1 - p(e_i))) - dp(e_i) \text{ ((11)) with } \ln(p(e_i)/(1 - p(e_i))) = -e_i/T \text{ FD case}$$

Summing ((11)) then leads to 0. There is a link between energy and information which is also present in the reaction balance approach.

Why Should Information Be Conserved?

Physically, one may readily argue that one may have a conserved energy and particle number in a gas. In such a case, $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ (i.e. physical fluctuations) cannot violate these conserved quantities. In the MB case, however,

$\ln(N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!) \quad ((12))$ is not a conserved quantity.

Different sets of $n(e_i) = Np(e_i)$ yield different $\ln(\text{total number of state values})$. We note that one may only consider $p(e_i)$ sets which satisfy $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i p(e_i) e_i = e_{ave} = E/N$. Applying Stirling's approximation does not change the fact that $((12))$ is not a conserved quantity. Considering a special $p(e_i)$ set which maximizes $((12))$ and still obeys the particle number and energy constraints, however, is equivalent to conserved quantity because one cannot increase or decrease the maximum number of states. In the Stirling approximation, this translates to the fact that one cannot increase or decrease the total information (now written as an average like in the energy case). Thus, it does seem that information is conserved, but this means that it takes on an extreme value, i.e. one has as little information as possible. Thus, the notion of conserved information is consistent with maximization of entropy subject to constraints.

Conclusion

In conclusion, one traditionally maximizes entropy subject to constraints (usually of conserved quantities such as particle number and energy) in order to find the form of a distribution $p(e_i)$. Entropy is taken to be $\ln(\text{number of states})$ in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $\ln(N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!)$. If one uses Stirling's approximation: $\ln(n(e_i)!) = n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i))$, then $\ln(\text{number of states})$ essentially becomes minus the sum of average information. If information is minimized, then entropy is maximized. A minimized average information is, however, equivalent to information being a conserved quantity, just like energy and particle number, we argue. Conservation of energy is written in terms of $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$, i.e. an average and conservation of information is written in the same manner: $\sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i))$ (MB case). Thus, one may consider that one has three interrelated conserved quantities: information, energy and particle number. Formally, maximizing entropy subject to constraints of conserved quantities, means that: $d \sum_i p(e_i) = 0$ and $d \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = 0$. Thus, $d \sum_i p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) = 0$ and one has a conserved quantity.

We note that the idea of entropy thought of in terms of conserved information carries over to the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases, where one now has two physical probabilities $p(e_i)$ and $(1-p(e_i))$ instead of one and so writes two average information terms.